

AM1 Study of the Reaction Paths of Formamidine

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Semi-empirical AM1 method has been successfully applied to study the decomposition and 1,3-sigmatropic reactions of formamidine. While the decomposition reaction is predicted to be asynchronous, 1,3-sigmatropic shift is predicted to be synchronous.

Study of the reaction paths of amidines is of considerable interest since these compounds are important for the synthesis of heterocycles and these compounds also serve as useful models to study the active centre of the enzyme lactate dehydrogenase¹. Formamidine can undergo different types of reactions. It can isomerise from *endo*- to *exo*-form. It can also participate in antarafacial symmetry allowed 1,3-sigmatropic shift. It can also decompose giving HCN and NH₃. The mechanistic aspect of the decomposition of formamidine (Scheme 1) has been a matter of large number of theoretical investigations²⁻⁴. In the present work we have investigated the reaction paths of formamidine using molecular orbital (MO)

method. AM1⁵ method has been used in the present study. The calculated results have been compared with the results of available ab initio studies with a view to examine the adequacy of AM1 method.

Results and Discussion

Calculated equilibrium geometries for the *endo*- and *exo*-forms of formamidine are given in Table 1. Good agreement can be seen between the results of the present study and those obtained from earlier 4-31G calculations⁴. The activation barrier for *endo*-*exo* isomerisation is predicted to be 23.5 kcal mol⁻¹ while the energy separation between the two is only 4.7 kcal mol⁻¹.

The mechanistic aspect of the decomposition of formamidine to ammonia and hydrogen cyanide (Scheme 1) has been examined by studying the transition state (TS1) involved in the process. Selected bond lengths and bond angles for the transition state (TS1) are given in Table 2. Our calculated results are in good agreement with the results of 4-31G calculations². The transition state (TS2) involved in the 1,3-sigmatropic shift has also been examined and the calculated equilibrium geometries are given in Table 2 along with results of 4-31G calculations⁶. Here, again good agreement can be seen between the two results. Calculated activation barriers for these two reactions (i.e. decomposition and 1,3-hydrogen shift) are listed in Table 2. Excellent agreement can be seen with the results of 4-31G calculations.

Scheme 1

TABLE 1- CALCULATED EQUILIBRIUM GEOMETRIES AND HEAT OF FORMATION OF FORMAMIDINE*

	Calculated value	
	AMI ^a	4-31G ^b
Length (Å)		
C ₁ -N ₂	1.289(1.298)	1.262
C ₁ -N ₄	1.384(1.379)	1.367
N ₂ -H ₃	0.997(0.996)	1.007
C ₁ -H ₅	1.117(1.119)	1.073
Angle (degrees)		
N ₄ -C ₁ -N ₂	131.02(123.60)	128.83
Heat of Formation (kcal mol ⁻¹)	12.6(17.3)	

*See Fig. 1.

^aNumbers in parenthesis are for the *exo*-geometry.^bObtained from reference [1].

TABLE 2- CALCULATED EQUILIBRIUM GEOMETRIES FOR THE TRANSITION STATES AND ENERGY OF ACTIVATION

	Calculated value	
	AMI	4-31G ^a
<i>Decomposition reaction :</i>		
Length (Å)		
C ₁ -N ₂	1.254	1.240
C ₁ -N ₄	1.496	1.545
N ₂ -H ₃	1.525	1.465
N ₄ -H ₃	1.319	1.276
C ₁ -H ₅	1.093	1.068
Angle (degrees)		
N ₄ -C ₁ -N ₂	102.93	105.58
Energy of activation (kcal mol ⁻¹)	78.4	79.6
<i>1,3-Sigmatropic shift :</i>		
Length (Å)		
C ₁ -H ₅	1.098	1.071
C ₁ -N ₂	1.329	1.309
N ₂ -H ₃	0.977	0.991
N ₂ -H ₇	1.377	1.359
Angles (degrees)		
N ₂ -C ₁ -N ₄	99.24	105.10
H ₃ -N ₂ -C ₁	126.99	126.80
Energy of activation (kcal mol ⁻¹)	63.3	59.2

*See Fig. 1.

^aObtained from Refs. 2 and 6.

Calculated net charges on atoms of the reactants and the transition states involved in the decomposition and 1,3-hydrogen shift of formamidine are listed in Table 3. It can be seen from Table 3 that during decomposition, the carbon atom loses its positively charged character along the reaction profile.

The positive charge on hydrogen (H₃) increases while going from the reactant to the transition state. This suggests a more likely 'protonic' transfer than the transfer of a 'radical like' species. For 1,3-hydrogen shift the charge on migrating hydrogen increases and reaches its peak value at the transition state (see Table 3). Here again the process is more likely a 'protonic one'.

TABLE 3 - NET CHARGES ON ATOMS OF THE SPECIES INVOLVED IN THE REACTIONS OF FORMAMIDINE

Atom ^a	Charge	
	Reactant	T.S
<i>Decomposition reaction :</i>		
C ₁	0.075	-0.138
N ₂	-0.328	-0.327
H ₃	0.132	0.291
N ₄	-0.462	-0.298
H ₅	0.153	0.170
H ₆	0.219	0.151
H ₇	0.210	0.151
<i>1,3-Sigmatropic shift :</i>		
C ₁	0.071	0.083
N ₂	-0.341	-0.504
H ₃	0.145	0.196
N ₄	-0.420	-0.504
H ₅	0.095	0.157
H ₆	0.222	0.196
H ₇	0.228	0.376

^aSee Fig. 1.

Selected bond orders for the reactants and transition states involved in the decomposition and 1,3-hydrogen shift reactions are given in Table 4. The progress of the decomposition reaction was followed by an analysis of the bond orders given in Table 4. It is worthwhile to note that the sum of C₁-N₂ and C₁-N₄ bond orders is fairly conserved during the decomposition process. Similar is also the case for the sum of N₂-H₃ and N₄-H₃ bond orders. For 1,3-hydrogen shift reaction, the sum of C₁-N₂ and C₁-N₄ bond order is also fairly conserved during the course of reaction. To follow the nature of the reactions we have employed a More O'Ferrall-Jencks type ^{7,8} diagram. The results for the decomposition reaction are shown in Fig. 1 and those for 1,3-hydrogen shift are shown in Fig. 2. The reaction paths, Reactant → T.S. and T.S → Product, are described by the slopes α and α' . The α

TABLE 4—SELECTED BOND ORDERS OF THE SPECIES IN THE REACTIONS OF FORMAMIDINE

Bond ^a	Reactant	T.S.	Product	
			HCN	NH ₃
<i>Decomposition reaction :</i>				
C ₁ -N ₂	1.850	2.146	2.969	—
C ₁ -N ₄	1.070	0.798	0.000	—
N ₄ -H ₃	0.007	0.483	—	0.975
N ₂ -H ₃	0.944	0.404	—	0.000
<i>1,3-Sigmatropic shift :</i>				
C ₁ -N ₂	1.826	1.471	1.115	—
C ₁ -N ₄	1.115	1.471	1.826	—
N ₄ -H ₇	0.906	0.408	0.003	—
N ₂ -H ₇	0.003	0.408	0.906	—

^aSee Fig. 1.and α' values (see Fig. 1) for the decomposition

reaction are respectively 0.56 and 1.81. This indicates an asynchronous mechanism for decomposition. The α and α' values for 1,3-hydrogen shift (see Fig.2) are identical (0.79) indicating a synchronous mechanism. These predictions of present AMI studies are also consistent with the earlier findings of ab initio calculations.

Conclusions : The results of the present studies can be summarised as follows. (i) The difference in the energy of the *endo*- and *exo*-forms of formamidine is small but the barrier height for isomerisation is about 24 kcal mol⁻¹. (ii) The barrier height for decomposition is large (78.4 kcal mol⁻¹) and this explains why extreme conditions are necessary

Fig. 1. Decomposition of formamidine P (I, J) is the bond order for the I-J bond.

Fig. 2. 1,3-Hydrogen shift of formamidine. $P(I, J)$ is the bond order for the I-J bond.

for the decomposition of formamidine. The reaction is predicted to be an asynchronous one. (iii) The 1,3-hydrogen shift in formamidine is predicted to be a synchronous process with a barrier height of $63.3 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$.

The results of present AM1 study are in excellent agreement with the results of earlier ab initio calculations. It appears from the present study that the computationally inexpensive AM1 method can be successfully used to study the reaction paths of formamidine.

Calculations :

Calculations were carried out using MOPAC⁹ programme (Version 6.0) on a Hewlett-Packard 9000

series 500 model computer. The force constant matrix was examined for each transition state. In each case only one negative eigenvalue was found for force constant matrix. PRECISE option has been used for all calculations.

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